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DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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Annotation: In the current digital age, technology has become an essential component of our everyday lives. Even children are growing up surrounded by technological devices and online platforms. As a result, in the primary school, teachers are employing cutting-edge teaching techniques appropriate for their students' developmental stage. Carefully introducing technology education is necessary. This article examines the pedagogical approaches for teaching technology to primary and secondary education's students, drawing from current best practices in the field.

Keywords: primary education, secondary education, digital, technology, pedagogy, methods.

Introduction: In the 21st century, technology has become an integral part of our lives. Communication and with the world around us, from entertainment to education and healthcare changed our relationship. As a result, our children are based on technology equipping everyone with the skills and knowledge they need to thrive in the world is more important than ever.

Secondary schools are using more and more digital tools to improve teaching and learning as the educational landscape evolves quickly. With secondary schools serving as the primary focus of this study, educators are actively engaged in digital transformation initiatives across a range of areas, cognisant of the opportunities and challenges presented by the digital world. Significant data gaps are reduced at the national and international levels by utilising digital technology. They improve the integration of decision-making processes and prioritisation by facilitating the generation of real-time information and predictive analytics. Additionally, these technologies provide for insightful policy effectiveness feedback, which promotes ongoing optimisation and improvement.

Learning methods are constantly relying more and more on modern technologies is gradually improving. This advanced communication makes it easy to get information and makes it easier to explain the topic. Due to 21st century teaching methods to teachers it is easier to impart knowledge as well as

to recognize the potential of their students. On the other hand, through the use of audio-visual and interactive software and gadgets it becomes very easy for students to learn. This strategy of technology and teaching synergy opens up new opportunities in education and some methods are particularly noteworthy deserves.

More participation, quicker evaluation, and an immediate learning environment are all benefits of traditional classroom education. However, technology and digital learning resources connect these gaps. The efficiency that technology offers surpasses that of conventional teaching methods. The public is starting to use smartphones and other wireless devices more frequently. It makes sense for educational organisations like schools to effectively integrate technology into the teaching and learning process.

Distance Education: Distance education as a form of education has been around for decades used, but with the rapid development of means of communication, it gained importance.

Now, from the other side of the planet, you can attend classes in real time and even be active and participate. A lot types of smart devices (gatgets, laptops, phones and so on) for online education are very comfortable and we need have an internet connection and adequate communication software.

Educational technology includes virtual attendance, live chat, as well as teachers provides real-time face-to-face communication with students. In addition, there are previous lessons learned as well as many other study materials.

This teaching method is used in many American schools, sometimes as an additional teaching method used as, and sometimes those are the possibilities full-time online education. It has expanded so much that now there are even school extracurricular activities in this way for participating to students. And even students can graduate in many schools across the US in this way.

Computers and tablets in classes:

What would education look like without books? It is easy to answer this question, all information is placed on a tablet (or computer). Educational content digitization makes information easier to access, whereas photocopy textbooks are now will not be significant.

In addition, computers and tablets help in the following ways:

- ❖ they literally make learning easier (no heavy bags);
- ❖ ease of access anytime, anywhere;
- ❖ they provide a high level of computer literacy;
- ❖ they read by allowing children to use multimedia materials facilitates;

- ❖ Exposure to new technologies from an early age is great for further education serves as preparation;
 - ❖ computer-based test to assess knowledge for teachers facilitates.
- Of course, they must use tablets or computers to make all this possible for students and teachers

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